

A Novel Framework for Proactive CNF Orchestration in 6G NTN

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Abstract—The increasing complexity of 5G and beyond networks, particularly with the integration of Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs), demands more dynamic and intelligent approaches to Radio Access Network (RAN) optimization. This paper presents a novel framework for closed-loop NTN RAN optimization centered on proactive Containerized Network Function (CNF) orchestration. By leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) to anticipate virtual resource needs, the proposed framework enables efficient, real-time deployment and scaling of CNFs, significantly enhancing the resilience and adaptability of NTN systems. Our architecture leverages Machine Learning to predict crucial metrics such as CPU usage, memory, and bandwidth, and pre-allocate virtual resources, thereby reducing latency associated with reactive orchestration methods. This proactive approach ensures optimal allocation of limited NTN resources, improves network performance, and mitigates cold-start delays of containers. Through experimental analysis of AI-based forecasting models, our work proposes a proactive framework for CNF orchestration, demonstrating its potential to enable sustainable, scalable, and efficient CNF optimization tailored for 6G NTN solutions.

Index Terms—NTN, RAN, VNF, CNF, optimization, 6G, network orchestration, resource provisioning, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of mobile networks beyond 5G is introducing innovative methods to enhance network performance and adapt to growing demands. One significant advancement in New Radio (NR) Radio Access Networks (RAN) is the adoption of closed-loop optimization, [1]. This concept introduces an automated feedback system in which optimization functions within the RAN collect real-time data on network conditions, analyze these data, and execute adjustments to optimize performance. Closed-loop optimization is especially beneficial in Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs), where network infrastructure includes satellites, drones, or other non-ground-based platforms with inherently limited resources and higher latencies. These RAN optimization functions can operate in 5G as Virtual Network Functions (VNFs), which run on virtualized computational resources, making the entire optimization process both adaptable and scalable.

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The envisioned integration of TNs and NTNs for ubiquitous and continuous service in the IMT-2030 [2] further increase the complexity of network management and orchestration. This complexity cannot be managed by virtualization alone but requires an enhanced and more scalable technology, such as containerization: as we move toward 6G, the spotlight shifts to Cloud native Network Functions (CNFs) [3] also referred to as Containerized Network Functions, which promise even greater scalability and efficiency to the RAN optimization functions. Numerous strategies exist for CNF allocation, including static and dynamic approaches. However, these methods tend to be reactive, adjusting resources only when predefined thresholds are surpassed, resulting in potential delays. The use of AI opens the door to proactive management, enabling dynamic forecasting that can anticipate resource needs before thresholds are even reached, ensuring smoother performance and more efficient scaling tailored to 6G NTNs [4].

In the framework of CNF-based NTN RAN optimization, this paper introduces a novel architecture for proactive CNF orchestration, leveraging AI to dynamically forecast resource demand. Using Machine Learning (ML) models, our framework can predict time-series data for critical metrics such as CPU usage, memory consumption, and bandwidth requirements. These predictions enable the orchestrator to allocate resources in advance, reducing cold start delays [5] and ensuring a smoother scaling process.

The contributions of our work are:

- 1) **A novel framework for CNF orchestration in NTN**, embedding AI as a native component to enable proactive network management. This framework also includes an architecture for Machine Learning operations (MLOps) designed to train, re-train, save, and deploy machine learning models within the network environment. Additionally, the integration of the CNF orchestrator in the NTN architecture ensures dynamic resource allocation and management, providing enhanced flexibility and scalability, essential for the complex NTN ecosystem.
- 2) **AI/ML-based solutions for time-series resource forecasting**, enabling anticipatory scaling decisions to efficiently manage both overprovisioning and underprovisioning scenarios.

Fig. 1: NTN System Architecture.

II. RELATED WORK

The concept of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) has become fundamental in 5G networks, making optimal orchestration essential to manage the increasing complexity of these systems. Recent works highlight the necessity of AI for efficient VNF placement. For example, [6] emphasises the importance of AI-driven solutions to optimise VNF placement and orchestration, laying the groundwork for future networks. Similarly, [4] proposes an Orchestration Framework that leverages machine learning across the entire NFV environment. However, the paper does not provide results regarding the performance of its AI modules. In [7], a taxonomy is provided for ML-based orchestration, proposing a reference architecture to control overall resource utilisation, energy efficiency, and application performance. The authors stress the critical role of AI in improving VNF/CNF placement, achieving higher accuracy, and reducing computation delays.

Many existing studies focus on VNF placement in both TN and NTN [8], [9], [10], often treating it as a mathematical optimization problem. Some of them aim to optimize VNF placement through AI algorithms, using deep reinforcement learning [11], or clustering data into VNF profiles [12]. However, these solutions primarily offer reactive orchestration, where VNF placement adjusts only after resource thresholds are exceeded.

A proactive approach, especially in containerized environments, would be more efficient, as it can reduce cold start delays. Bianchini et al. [13] proposes an ML-centric platform called Resource Central (RC) for cloud resource management. RC has proven that ML techniques outperform traditional methods, offering more accurate predictions and better resource allocation in a generic cloud-based environment. However, the effectiveness of RC has been proven in a generic cloud-based environment without mentioning network data. Similarly, [14] employs machine learning models to predict incoming traffic in a 5G O-RAN environment, aiming to optimise VNF placement and scaling of virtual resources. Although this is a successful example of proactive orchestration, the authors acknowledge the challenge of model generalisation, where conventional supervised learning models

struggle with dynamic environments, often resulting in poor performance when handling new scenarios.

Only a few studies specifically address CNF placement. Kazemifard et al. [15] presents a mathematical model for CNF placement in O-RAN, improving end-to-end delay in data plane operations under resource-constrained environments. Another notable example, [5], uses a model-free Q-Learning reinforcement learning agent to optimise container instances in serverless environments. Additionally, [16] explores dynamic resource allocation for Kubernetes clusters through ML, including more advanced Deep Neural Networks.

Even though many studies focus on dynamic approaches for CNF/VNF allocation, often leveraging advanced algorithms, they still react to events only after they occur. To address this limitation, our framework centers on proactive orchestration, using AI/ML to anticipate network function resource needs in a containerized context. This proactive approach effectively manages both overprovisioning and underprovisioning scenarios, ensuring CNFs are allocated with the exact resources they require. This capability is essential in NTN, where onboard resources are limited, making it critical to reduce energy consumption while maintaining network QoS.

III. NTN SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

In this work, we consider an architecture that includes both TN and NTN access segments, and the network segment, as depicted in Figure 1. The NTN access segment consists of different NTN payloads, which are network elements on-board satellites that orbit the Earth at different altitudes providing services to on-ground users. It also includes NTN Gateways (GW) that interconnect the payload with the network segment via a feeder link.

Different types of NTN payloads can be identified. If the payload is able to perform radio frequency filtering, frequency conversion and amplification, as well as demodulation/decoding, switching and/or routing, it is called *regenerative*. On the other hand, if the payload implements only frequency conversion, filtering, and amplification, forwarding only RF signals between the GW and UEs, it is called *transparent*. Rel. 19 of 3GPP foresees the standardization of features assuming regenerative payload [17]. This enables

Fig. 2: A novel framework for CNF orchestration, with AI as a native component of the architecture.

complete or partial implementation of the RAN protocol stack on the payload. The NTN access segment service is seamlessly integrated with the TN service, which is delivered via a network of terrestrial gNBs.

The network segment consists of the Core Network (CN), the compute nodes, and the CNF Orchestrator. The role of the compute nodes is to run the RAN optimization CNFs, which gather information about the network status and use it to select and implement the best RAN configurations that optimize RAN performance. Different types of compute nodes can be identified depending on their computational capabilities and their position in the network. A high-performance compute node is able to handle high complexity CNF but it is often built far from access segments, due to its centralized nature. However, nodes that are located at the edge of the network are inherently less powerful and are used to run CNFs that require fewer computational resources. To specifically support responsive optimization of the NTN access segment, in the context of this paper, satellite-based compute nodes are considered. These types of compute nodes introduce a variety of challenges due to the dynamic nature of Inter Satellite Links (ISL) and the limited computational power of satellite payloads. The multitude of compute nodes and their ever-changing compute loads, makes the optimal allocation of CNFs to different compute nodes a demanding task. In this context, the CNF orchestrator is introduced in the network segment to optimally allocate CNFs to the compute nodes based both on the nodes' computation availability and on the latency that is tolerated by the specific CNF.

Finally, in the user segment, we consider users directly connected to the NTN and TN elements through the Uu interface.

IV. A NOVEL FRAMEWORK FOR CNF ORCHESTRATION

In this section, we present the key components of our architecture for Cloud-native Network Function orchestration (Fig.2), where Artificial Intelligence (AI) is envisioned as a native component (described in detail in Fig. 3). The CNF orchestrator is designed to seamlessly manage both terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks and is incorporated into the network segment, as shown in Fig. 1.

A. CNF Orchestrator

The CNF Orchestrator (Fig. 2) is the core component responsible for managing the deployment and orchestration of VNFs in containers. In the context of NTN, the CNF Orchestrator is designed to address the unique challenges posed by satellite-based communication systems, such as high latency, dynamic link conditions, and limited computational resources onboard satellites. In our vision of 6G NTN, VNFs are deployed in containers and managed by Kubernetes. Kubernetes' ability to rapidly adapt to changing traffic patterns and network conditions is vital for ensuring optimal service delivery in NTN, particularly in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) constellations where constant handovers and network shifts occur.

Key components of the CNF Orchestrator include:

- **Monitoring System:** Continuous monitoring is essential for optimizing resource management and enhancing orchestration decisions. A monitoring tool like Prometheus tracks real-time metrics from CNFs deployed across both terrestrial and satellite nodes. It collects data such as CPU usage, memory consumption, and network bandwidth, which are crucial not only for operational management but also for providing the foundational data necessary for training machine learning models.
- **AI-Powered Network Forecasting:** It manages the full lifecycle of AI/ML operations to enable proactive resource management. It includes services for data collection and storage, database for historical and predicted metrics, and a machine learning platform for executing ML pipelines to forecast resource utilization across terrestrial and satellite environments. This module is shown in detail in Figure 3, and each subcomponent is explained in the following section.
- **Orchestration Engine:** This customised orchestrator powered by AI, overrides Kubernetes' default autoscaler to implement a proactive scaling strategy. By utilising forecasting data it facilitates faster container deployments, reduces cold start delays, and prevents both overprovisioning and underprovisioning of resources. This proactive approach ensures that both terrestrial and non-terrestrial resources are allocated efficiently.

B. The AI-powered Network Forecasting

The AI-powered Network Forecasting module (Fig. 3) is designed to handle the full lifecycle of AI/ML operations, consisting of several key services:

- **Data Collection Storage:** This service extracts time series captured by the Monitoring System and stores them in the Prediction Storage Service for further processing. It ensures that relevant performance metrics are continuously captured from both terrestrial and non terrestrial nodes, and readily available for future analysis.
- **Prediction Storage Service:** This service is responsible for storing both the historical input data used for Machine Learning and the outputs of the Machine Learning

Fig. 3: Detailed architecture of the proposed AI-Powered Network Forecasting component.

pipelines. A time series database is preferred for this service due to its optimization for handling time-based data, enabling efficient storage and retrieval of both input data and forecasting results.

- **Machine Learning Platform:** It manages the execution of ML pipelines, specifically designed to forecast container resource utilization across terrestrial and satellite environments. It adheres to established standards for ML operations [18], encompassing the entire lifecycle, from data loading and preprocessing to model training and inference.
- **Machine Learning Function Orchestrator (MLFO):** It automates the scheduling, monitoring, and tracking of ML workflows, streamlining the development and deployment process. MLFO tools like Prefect help maintain the flow of operations across distributed systems and support seamless integration with other components.
- **Deployment Storage:** This system serves as the repository for machine learning models and associated artifacts. It is implemented using high-performance object storage solutions, such as MinIO, to ensure secure, scalable, and fast access to these resources, supporting real-time retrieval and updates.
- **Execution Environment:** The execution of ML pipelines is managed within Docker containers to ensure consistent and isolated runtime environments for all pipelines. These containers allow ML models to run in a controlled and

reproducible manner, enabling a parallel and efficient execution of pipelines.

V. AI FOR CNF RESOURCE FORECASTING

In this section, we analyze the AI models utilized for time series forecasting, which are **ARIMA** (AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average), **GRU** (Gated Recurrent Unit), **univariate LSTM** (Long Short-Term Memory), **multivariate LSTM**. We selected these model classes considering their ability to handle historical data patterns and their applicability to our specific use case. We evaluate and compare the performances of all models. To promote transparency and reproducibility, all experiments are open source and available in our GitHub repository [19].

A. Dataset Overview

All models were trained and evaluated on the same dataset to ensure a fair comparison of performance metrics. The initial dataset, publicly available [20], contains collected metrics from three types of applications running in a cloud-native environment. Among these, the collection of metrics from the OpenAirInterface 5G Core network function AMF (Access and Mobility Management Function), was found to be particularly relevant for our experiments, as it represents a good example of a network function that can be deployed in containers. Before training, we applied a few preprocessing steps: we downsampled the data, we applied interpolation to handle null

values, and we split the resulting dataset into two sets, 70% for training and 30% for testing.

B. Experimental Setup

The experiments simulate a real-world scenario, where historical resource usage metrics are available, and the objective is to predict the resource usage for the next time period. During the testing phase, we iterate through the test set, predicting one step ahead each time. After making each prediction, the true value from the test set is added to the training data, simulating a real-time forecasting scenario where new data continuously becomes available. This allows us to test how well each machine learning model adapts to new information. We trained the ML models using different downsampling frequencies and evaluated their ability to forecast both CPU and memory usage by comparing them to our **baseline**, which is a simple average over the entire test set. The models are evaluated using three performance metrics:

- **Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE):** Measures the accuracy of the predictions as a percentage error.
- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE):** Provides the average magnitude of the errors in a dataset without considering their direction.
- **Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE):** Highlights larger errors by squaring the error terms, emphasising deviations that may be more impactful in practice.

C. Results

The results are shown in Table I. ARIMA (Fig. 5a), produced a MAPE of 0.32 for both CPU and memory, performing even worse than the baseline. This suggests that the pure statistical method is not able to capture underlying patterns and it only adds noise on top of the data. Next, we evaluated GRU and LSTM for univariate forecasting. Interestingly, when predicting CPU usage, both models showed a significant improvement over the baseline (Fig.4a, Fig.4b), with MAPE values of 0.21 and 0.22. However, for memory usage, these models only provided a slight improvement, maintaining the same MAPE but achieving lower MAE and RMSE compared to the baseline (Fig.5b). This reveals that CPU time series has simpler patterns that can be predicted using a single variable, while memory usage has more complex patterns that need additional variables to achieve significant improvements over the baseline. In fact, when moving to a multivariate forecasting (Fig.4c, Fig.5c), where the LSTM model is provided with additional related variables, we observed a significant improvement in performance for both CPU and memory usage, with a MAPE of 0.12 and 0.21, respectively. This indicates a clear relationship between the target variables (CPU, memory) and the additional covariates, demonstrating the benefits of incorporating multiple variables to capture interdependencies.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we proposed a novel framework for proactive CNF orchestration in NTN systems that leverages AI/ML techniques to forecast container resource usage, enabling a

Metric	Model	MAPE	MAE	RMSE
CPU	baseline	0.31	0.31	0.34
CPU	ARIMA	0.32	0.24	0.29
CPU	GRU	0.21	0.21	0.27
CPU	LSTM univariate	0.22	0.22	0.29
CPU	LSTM multivariate	0.12	0.09	0.12
memory	baseline	0.26	363	397
memory	ARIMA	0.32	366	400
memory	GRU	0.26	362	394
memory	LSTM univariate	0.26	355	392
memory	LSTM multivariate	0.21	271	323

TABLE I: Comparison of AI/ML Models. CPU is measured in GHz, memory is measured in MB.

(a) CPU usage with GRU

(b) CPU usage with univariate LSTM

(c) CPU usage with multivariate LSTM

Fig. 4: Comparison of CPU usage forecasts.

proactive approach to orchestration. Unlike reactive strategies, which respond to resource changes after they occur, our approach anticipates demand to optimize performance and resource efficiency. Utilizing the proposed CNF orchestration enhances the efficiency managing RAN functions, a critical factor for meeting the stringent requirements of 6G-integrated TN and NTN. Additionally, we evaluated and compared multiple AI models for resource usage forecasting, using a publicly available dataset. Our results show that the multivariate approach outperforms any univariate approach, indicating dependencies between various resource usage metrics (e.g.,

(a) Memory usage with ARIMA

(b) Memory usage with GRU

(c) Memory usage with multivariate LSTM

Fig. 5: Comparison of memory usage forecasts.

CPU, memory, bandwidth). Nonetheless, both approaches are promising and could significantly assist a CNF orchestrator in proactively allocating virtual resources to deploy network functions, leading to optimal use of energy and network infrastructure, a critical factor in NTN.

For future work, we plan to adopt this architecture in a real 5G/6G environment, experimenting it in a testbed to collect live metrics and fully integrate the AI-Powered Network Forecasting module with a CNF orchestrator engine. This would allow us to assess whether the performance improvements observed in this work using the open dataset align with real-world scenarios. Additionally, we aim to improve the AI-Powered Network Forecasting architecture by separating the training and inference phases of ML models. This facilitates the adoption of more sophisticated models that require extensive training while optimizing the retraining frequency. Retraining only when model performance begins to degrade, reduces the number of training cycles and conserves energy while maintaining prediction accuracy. This approach will make the system more efficient for adoption in real network environments, enabling the deployment of predictors closer to where they are really needed, independently from energy constraints, such as on satellites.

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